

GOND PAINTINGS: REFLECTION OF CULTURE OF GOND TRIBE OF MADHYA PRADESH

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ABSTRACT

Gond paintings reflect the rich cultural heritage of the Gond tribe from Madhya Pradesh, India. Rooted in the tribe's Dravidian origins, this vibrant folk art has been passed down for over 1400 years, capturing the Gonds' connection to nature, mythology, and social beliefs. Traditionally painted on the walls and floors of homes during festivals, Gond art is now also created on paper and canvas, thanks to pioneering artists like Jangarh Singh Shyam. With its intricate designs and vivid colors, Gond painting celebrates the tribe's deep cultural traditions and positive worldview.

Keywords: Gond Tribe, Folk Art, Madhya Pradesh, Cultural Heritage, Gond Paintings

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INTRODUCTION

Human emotions, expression and association are important objective of art. Tribal art is renowned for its instantaneous and strong artistic impression, which is marked by its use of hues, humour, complexity, and mystery. The largest Adivasi community in India is made up of the Gonds, who hail from the pre-Aryan era as a Dravidian people. The term 'Gond', originated from 'Kond', is linked with the Green Mountains in Dravidian tradition. The name reflects the lifestyle of Gond people who live in lush and mountainous areas and is sometimes called 'Koi' or 'Koitur'. Nature's preserved beauty is shown in these mountains, which can be a source of inspiration and food for all living beings. The majority of their presence can be found in Madhya Pradesh and the states surrounding it.

Gond painting is a folk art form that is both colorful and skillful in conveying the core concepts of conversational language Thamanna and Subramani (2023). The creative intuition of the Gond tribe in central India is reflected in Gond painting. They record the relationship between their cosmic, natural, social, and religious worlds. The traditional belief is that seeing a good image brings good luck. The Gond people have a tradition of painting the mud walls and floors of their house with beautiful depiction during religious festivals and special occasions because of this belief Goswami (2018).

Gond art is a cultural treasure of India that dates back to the Mesolithic Period and can be traced back to over 1400 years. The Gond artists claim that their art is a celebration of their deeply rooted cultural tradition. The viewer is elicited by the rich colours in the compositions, which convey a sense of great pleasure and positivity. These paintings are notable for their delicate and vibrant designs, which often portray elements of nature, animals, customs, and mythology Thamanna and Subramani (2023).

Gond painting in its modern form began as a decorative and symbolic art, which was known as 'Dighna' during the Gond festival. The Gond tribe cites Dighna as having the power to fight evil and radiant positive energy and thus uses it extensively during religious festivals and marriages Goswami (2018). The village of Patangarh in Dindori district is home to artists, and it is indebted to the artistic legacy of Gond artist Jangarh Singh Shyam and other famous Gond artists Gond (2022). Janagarh Singh Shyam marked the start of Gond artists creating art on paper and canvas Thamanna and Subramani (2023).

HISTORICAL BACKGROUND

Gonds are the primeval tribal community engaged in hunting and food gathering, agriculture, martial tasks, basic trade and commerce, herbal medicine as well as ruled in Middle India. This tribe makes up 13.45 percent of India's total scheduled tribes' population.

In the 14th and 15th century AD, the first historically recorded Gond kingdoms were established in the hilly region of middle India. The Gond realm was first conquered by Jadurai, who overthrew the Kalchuri Rajputs to obtain Garha Mandla (1300 to 1789 AD). King Jatba ruled the second kingdom of Deogarh from 1590 AD to 1796 AD. Deogarh and the Kherla kingdom both appeared in 1500 AD and remained in existence for a century. The Gonds ruled over a large kingdom in central India for many centuries and established their own social, religious, and cultural foundation during that time Koreti (2016).

The Gond community has been residing in the Narmada region of the Vindhya, Satpura and Mokal, in Amarkantak, for a long time in Madhya Pradesh. In the 14th century, the Gond had power in various parts of central India and constructed forts, palaces, temples, tanks, and lakes Goswami (2018).

CULTURAL SIGNIFICANCE

Gond paintings, which are traditionally made on celebratory occasions, portray different celebrations, rituals, and how humans interact with nature. By combining dots and lines, this mystical art form is created. The still images are brought to life with the imaginative use of lines. It is in the community's interest to be surrounded by beauty, as they hold the belief those who view a good image, good fortune will befall them. They don't make art just for the aesthetic pleasure but it also establish a continuity between the past and the present. In this way process of painting is considered as a spiritual prayer. The paintings are not just an expression of nature worship, but also a means of protection and preventing evil.

The multi-colored, dot-bright grandeurs of tribal gods, birdy creatures, anthill-covered alligators, and long-snouted crabs are both creative and imaginative. Their beliefs revolve around the purity of their surroundings - it is the source of their livelihood and survival. Their art is comprised of their companions, namely animals, birds, and insects, who inhabit their legends, art, and music.

STYLE AND TECHNIQUES

The majority of Gond tribal paintings in Madhya Pradesh were made on the walls of houses. The paintings commence from the bottom of the wall and reach a height of eight to ten feet. To prepare the surface for painting, the wall is plastered with a mixture of black or white clay and cow dung. In local language the clay is called guru or gar. Once the wall is dry, painting is done using a cotton swab or a cloth tied to a twig from a neem or babul tree Bharadwaj (2014).

Gond paintings involve a colour palette that is bright and vibrant, with red, yellow, black, blue, green, purple, and white as primary colours, reflecting their positive outlook on life. The local sand known as Chui mitti provides the yellow in Gond paintings, brown is obtained from Gheru mitti, green is obtained from leaves, and red is obtained from the Hibiscus flower Thamanna and Subramani (2023). Natural sources are utilized for the paints, including charcoal, colored soil, plant sap and leaves, and cow dung Gond (2022).

After the flat colour application is finished, the images are completely transformed with utmost perfection by adding lines with other colours. With the continuous movement of lines, the spectator's eyes glide smoothly from one point to another Saxena (2017).

Gond paintings are distinguished by their intricate patterns and vibrant hues which is the hallmark of Gond art. To enhance movement perception and depth, dots and dashes are added according to Thamanna and Subramani (2023).

Paper and canvas are now being used by the painters for storytelling. Visual ideas are built through a rough pencil outline. After the canvas is filled with flat areas of bright acrylic colours, small patterns reminiscent of women's tattoos begin to appear. Just like song's vibrations and fables within stories, coloured dots and lines chase each other in close succession. Immeasurable patience and delicate brush strokes are part of the mediation process, as though reliving past days Bharadwaj (2014).

THEMES

It is believed in Gond art that a well-designed image can bring fortune. Everything in the Gond religious system, including hills, rivers, rocks, and trees, is considered sacred because it is believed to be the residence of a spirit. Thus, the Gond tribe shows deep respect and endearment for these elements.

Gond art often represents the region's rich flora and fauna, and animals such as peacocks, birds, crabs, and various mythical creatures that play a major role. Gond artists incorporate elements such as airplanes, bicycles, and cars into their artwork, blending tradition with modernity. The cultural diversity of the region can be seen in the portrayal of Hindu gods and deities, as well as local spiritual figures. Gond art has a strong connection to nature, with its focus on the connection between human life and the environment.

The creation of original artworks includes flowers, trees, and rendition of gods, goddesses, and devils. The painting of Dhignas and Bhittichitra on the ground and brick walls around people's houses is a way to convey their immediate devotion and faith, in addition to serving as ornamentation. Gond paintings were inspired from the subjects of regional celebrations and goddesses like Marahi Devi and Phulvari Devi (Goddess Kali), as well as local festival like Karwa Chauth, Deepawali, Ahoi Ashtami, Nag Panchmi, and Sanjhi. The depiction of Gods, humanity, animals, birds, horses, elephants, tigers, and other subjects are done in vivid, life-like colours Thamanna and Subramani (2023).

Conventional Gond art is comprised of dance, song, and painting. Folk songs are used for oral storytelling. Traditional string instruments like the Kingri and the Bana called Dhemse are also compatible with these. Through the songs, the religious history of the Gonds, their deities, and mythology are communicated. The purpose of their paintings is to worship nature and to seek protection and ward off evil. Mahua Tree is referred as 'The Tree of Life' and for Gond communities, it holds a special significance due to its value and ability to sustain life. The Mahua tree is clearly a significant contributor to the lives of the Gond people. They show their respect for this tree through their art Arur & Wyeld (2016).

GOND MYTHOLOGY

Gond art is still vibrant and carries tales from Gondi mythology and traditions. Gond-Pardhans have faith in the existence of both Devayoni (divine form) and Bhutayoni (ghost form, and have a credence in the atman (soul). Lord Shiva's encounter with the Mahua tree is one of their most cherished stories. Rupendra Shyam's painting of a Mahua tree adorned with fruit, crowned by a parrot, and flanked by dynamically portrayed boars and tigers is a stunning illustration. Lord Badadev's story is an essential component of Gond mythology Thamanna and Subramani (2023).

GOND ART OF MADHYA PRADESH

Madhya Pradesh is a state in India that has a large number of tribal communities. The state has a reputation for its tribal arts and crafts. The Anthropological evidences shows the continuance of Gond tribe in Gondwana –'Land of Gond' in the green mountains of Godavari gorges in the south to Vindhya mountains in the north. It is also considered as one of the largest tribe of South Asia. By the sixteenth century, their ruled continued in four kingdoms: Garha-Mandla, Deogarh, Chanda, and Kherla in central India. The Muslim invasion resulted in their migration to the forest regions of Vindhya and Satpura nearby. Using the 'Signature pattern' to fill in larger placements on the canvas is one of the distinctive elements. The characteristics of the Gonds are their individual signatures style comprises of repetitive lines, minute dots, chains, tiny circles, crosses or any type of strokes that can be repeated again and again Rastogi. et al. (2022).

The Gond paintings were originally painted on mud walls with natural colours, was refined by Pradhans in Patangarh village in Dindori District, Madhya Pradesh. Nature, wildlife, religious belief, mythology, and folklore were the main inspirations for Gond's paintings Goswami & Yadav (2019).

The Pardhan Gonds were known for their illustrious storytelling abilities in the Gond Tribal community. The task of passing down folklore and tribal stories in song, along with the sound of the stringed 'Bana', was delegated to them. In a literal way, Gond art is the representation of these songs as images of good luck. Playing the musical instrument known as the Bana, they pray and invoke God Bada Dev under the Saja tree Saxena (2017)

CONTRIBUTION OF ARTIST-

Janagarh Singh Shyam is known as the first Gond artist who created art on paper and canvas Thamanna and Subramani (2023). Patangarh is home to famous Gond painter Jagan Singh Shyam, with every family having at least one painter and everyone's life is centered around Gond art. In the 1980s, Jagdish SwamiNathan, a prominent artist and poet who set up Bharat Bhawan, met Jagan Shyam and invited him to Bhopal to work on a paper and canvas series, a distinctive creation that takes center stage at Bharat Bhawan Saxena (2017).

His efforts brought him worldwide fame with exhibitions of Gond paintings in Tokyo, Paris, and other locations. He later made it his goal to instruct others to pursue this art as a profession. Jangarh Singh Shyam's legacy is still alive, most notably in the next generation of Shyams whom he taught how to traditional Gond painting Goswami (2018).

MODERN APPROACH OF GOND PAINTING

The Gond artist have already shifted from native pigments to readily available art supplies in the market. This discovery was made by late artist J. Swaminathan in the 1980s during the development and establishment of Bharat Bhawan in Bhopal. This event marked the start of 'Jangarh Kalam', an entirely new form of painting that is rooted in Gond tribal culture and has parallels to contemporary arts. Several government buildings in India and abroad feature large murals on their walls. The presence of new motifs such as cycles, aeroplanes, motorcycles, jeeps, buses, and guns in Gond paintings exemplifies the modernity and dynamic nature of folk paintings Bharadwaj (2014).

The Gond Painting is widely popular in its original canvas style, but not in apparel, accessories, or home furnishings. Therefore, the world is brimming with opportunities Saxena (2017). This painting can be done on apparel, whether it's by hand or using block printing, digital printing, heat transfer printing, or screen printing. To revive the painting, the government can train artisans in this field. Traditional gond paintings have been transformed by using technological tools and techniques to enhance their beauty. This will aid in the product's acceptance by consumers in the current market and provide employment for artisans only in their homes Bora (2017).

CONCLUSION

Gond art serves as a representation of the folklore they used to sing by visually depicting them through lines and dots with bold and vibrant colors. It is rooted in a traditional belief that viewing good images brings good fortune. It possesses the ability to ward off evils, and instills positivity in life. In the modern era, Gond art has progressed from traditional wall paintings to canvas and paper, even as a form of merchandise. With the support of government and other organizations, artists have got numerous opportunities to showcase their work on a global scale through exhibitions and trade fairs. Since the painting may be expensive, Gond art in the form of merchandise can be an easier way to attract customers. When presented in the form of apparels and accessories such as clothes and bags, it will attract more customers due to affordability and creativity. Thus, it becomes a way to preserve this heritage art and promote it on international platforms.

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